

RAMONES

Radioactivity Monitoring in Ocean Ecosystems

Deliverable

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Disclaimer

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RAMONES project's main objective is to close the current marine radioactivity gap in sampling and foster new interdisciplinary research in ocean ecosystems. RAMONES will invest a significant effort to provide tools to enable long-term data acquisition missions, rapid deployments, low cost per information byte, and propose new AI and Robotics-driven and supported methodologies, being ambitious to eventually offer scaled-up solutions to researchers, policy makers and communities. These goals will be achieved by combining state-of-the-art (SoA) methodologies and equipment from various disciplines in a well-balanced synergy. It will also design new and effective methodologies targeting the marine environment, which will provide efficient response to existing natural and man-made hazards, and shape future policies for the global population. RAMONES will additionally contribute to shaping a blueprint on Environmental Intelligence in the EU and worldwide.

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List of acronyms

Acronym	Description
AI	Artificial Intelligence
DB	Database
DL	Deep Learning
DMP	Data Management Plan
EIC	European Innovation Council
EU	European Union
FGDB	File geodatabase
F ² SS	Forecasting & Foresight Support System
FSS	Forecasting Support Systems
GIS	Geographical Information System
GO	Governmental Organization
IP	Intellectual Property
JA	Judgmental Adjustment
Maastricht	Treaty on the European Union
ML	Machine Learning
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
pF ² SS	Prototype Forecasting & Foresight Support System
POIS2ON	Prototype RAMONES Information System for SocioecONomic stakeholders
SF	Statistical Forecasts
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
SoA	State of the Art
SRF	Strategic Response Frameworks
WP	Work Package

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Abstract

RAMONES is an ambitious, high-risk project which aims to prove that innovative combination and advancement of recent developments in detector technology and sensor materials, low-power-autonomous robotic systems, and process-modelling theories, have the potential to overcome contemporary limitations and open the window to high temporal and spatial resolution underwater radioactivity measurements, in situ and in near real time, forming a game changer in deep-water environmental monitoring. RAMONES proposes a new generation of submarine radiation-sensing instruments, assisted by State of the Art (SoA) robotic and artificial intelligence (AI) solutions towards understanding radiation related risks near and far from coastal areas, while providing data for the international community towards shaping new policies and governance guidelines for environmental sustainability, economic growth, and human health.

One of the main goals also of RAMONES is to introduce novel monitoring and response channels to inform key socio-political and socio-economics stakeholders at regular intervals at medium (daily, weekly) to low (monthly to inter-annually) frequencies. To that end, the deliverable 5.1. of Work Package 5 provides the functional requirements for a prototype information system, hereafter referred to as **POIS2ON** (Prototype RAMONES Information System for SocioecONomic stakeholders), an amalgamation of the French words ‘fish’ and ‘poison’ to indicate the risk of deep sea anthropogenic and natural emitted radioactivity to our ecosystem and respective food chain.

POIS2ON will provide statistical forecasts and respective judgmental adjustments primarily for cumulative radionuclide concentrations as well as other time series monitoring hazardous activities and respective risks. The prototype system POIS2ON, a Forecasting Support System (FSS), also proposes at this stage two alternative architectures for a repository (and respective databases – DB and/or geodatabases - FGDB) for all recorded time series, with different levels of information concentration depending on the final form and capabilities of the technologies that will be developed from RAMONES. At a second stage and once Risk Indices have been developed too (deliverables D5.5 – D5.8) foresight capabilities will be added to the system (functional requirements provided in D5.5) leading to a complete Forecasting & Foresight Support System (F2SS) given the long-term nature of such activities. Finally, provision for spatio-temporal representation and visualization will be prescribed via connections to off-the-shelf GIS systems (Geographical Information Systems), using sharing patterns by providing a destination (e.g website, apps) where end users can access geospatial information and capabilities.

Keywords

RAMONES; POIS2ON; Radioactivity; Deep Water; Measurement; Forecasting; Risk.

1. Introduction

1.1 Context

This document belongs to Work Package 5 (WP5, *Citizen Awareness, Communication and Dissemination Activities*), and in particular to Task T5.1 *Forecasting and risk management* led by UDUR that is aiming to transliterate the in-situ, high frequency (e.g. multiple times per hour) measurements of radioactivity in deep ocean waters to actual time series that can be forecasted, estimating when general acceptable daily/weekly/monthly/annually limits are exceeded, and as such quantify the risk and potential impact to the environment and human populations.

POIS2ON (Prototype RAMONES Information System for SocioecONomic stakeholders), a forecasting & foresight support system (F2SS) system will be developed, which will include initially a decentralized Repository for recorded time series, to offer forecasted cumulative radionuclide concentrations, as well as other potentially dangerous elements concentrations at medium frequencies (daily & weekly) and the associated impact to relevant stakeholders: policy makers, regulatory agencies, governments, etc. This process will be fully automated and be able to run unsupervised at prescribed frequencies. Initially standard statistical techniques will be employed but given enough datapoints collected per time series, machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) methods will be used.

After consultation with IAEA and EU, and in the later phases of T5.1 as part of the linked deliverable due in month 27, D5.5 (Forecasting and Risk Assessment for awareness policy support no1), we will report on the functional requirements of a data-driven risk monitor at medium frequency for the awareness of interested stakeholders and communities. Health safety novel risk indices will be proposed: i) based on [Ni21] and cumulative Points-Over-Threshold that would give medium- to long-term forecasts for radioactivity - and other dangerous elements- levels, ii) based on [Be17] and real-time monitoring of radon emissions, and using value-at-risk measure and control charting, for short-term local policy response, and/or iii) based on [Ma13] and the use of a real options approach to examine the impact of abrupt increases in radioisotopes- related socio-economic costs for longer-term policy recommendation, legislation and adoption.

1.2 Structure of the document

From this point, the current document is organized according to the following structure and contents:

Section 2. Usage Scenarios and High-level Functional Requirements

Section 3. Detailed Functional Requirements

Section 4. Conclusion and the Future

1.3 Objectives and approach

The objectives of the RAMONES D5.1 deliverable is to set the functional requirement for the prototype information system **POIS2ON** that provides statistical forecasts and respective judgmental adjustments primarily for cumulative radionuclide concentrations, as well as other time series monitoring hazardous activities and respective risks. This deliverable states clearly and formally the functional requirements of the respective system, so essentially states WHAT the system should do, but not HOW, that is the core of the next deliverable D5.2 in six months' time that details the design of the prototype system. D5.1 serves as a foundation of what the prototype system should be able to do.

The prototype system, a Forecasting Support System (FSS), also proposes at this stage two alternative architectures for a repository (and respective databases – DB) for all recorded time series, with different levels of information concentration depending on the final form and capabilities of the technologies that will be developed from RAMONES. At a second stage and once Risk Indices have been developed too (deliverables D5.5 – D5.8) foresight capabilities will be added to the system (functional requirements provided in D5.5) leading to a complete Forecasting & Foresight Support System (F2SS) given the long-term nature of such activities. Finally, provision for spatio-temporal representation and visualization will be prescribed via connections to off-the-shelf GIS systems (Geographical Information Systems). GIS can visualize information products like 2d maps and 3D scenes and create geospatial analyses from geoprocessing models including vector-raster data, imagery and 3D data.

2. Usage Scenarios and High-level Functional Requirements

2.1 Usage Scenario 1

In our first usage scenario of POIS2ON, socioeconomic stakeholders (e.g. a **minister** of the government of the country where the area of interest belongs) depict **an area of interest** in the sea where **natural activity** takes place like an underwater **Volcano** – i.e. our first test-site in Kolumbo near Santorini Island in Greece –and respective risks are realized and need to be measured.

The area of interest is depicted in the sea (or as an extension to a lake, a river, or any water basin) in a map, by either indicating a polygon of (latitude, longitude) for each corner of the polygon (assuming the area extends from the surface to the sea basin for each point of interest), or at a future extension a polygon of (latitude, longitude, depth from surface from, depth from surface to) for each corner of the polygon essentially depicting a 3D polygonal object in the water, as well a starting time and ending time (date/time) of observation.

Then the RAMONES deployment team (given the scalability of our technology there will be many RAMONES teams ready for deployment in the future once our prototype proves its functionality till 2025) will break the 3D polygonal object into thousands of datapoints of (latitude, longitude, depth from surface) on which measurement will be made for the element(s) of interest (e.g. Rn-222), for the period of time of interest, at high frequencies per datapoints (many times per minute is the current estimation given the development of the technology).

These measurements will then be aggregated in a temporal fashion (at a lower frequency – a few times a day a cumulative measurement) and as a few datapoints or even one for the whole area of interest, resulting in one or very few timeseries measuring the elements of interest in the area of interest.

These times can then be forecasting with time series models (statistical benchmarks, ML plus DL more advanced models) and estimates of how soon annual limits might be exceeded and respective alarms can be raised and communicated to the respective socioeconomic stakeholders, and respective Strategic Response Frameworks (SRF) initiated.

Our measurements include (but not limited to - and are to be determined further during the course of the project depending on the success of our measurement technology):

- Cs-137
- Rn-222
- Ra-226
- Pb-214
- Pb-210
- Bi-214
- Tl-208m
- Pu-239/240
- Images – definitely from the static platforms and potentially from the mobile devices
- Mercury – assuming technology for sampling of water and or (live or dead) organisms will be developed. This might introduce of lags given these samples will be analysed - and reported back – in off-the-sea laboratories.

These measurements will have the form of high frequency time series stored in local decentralized databases/repositories in each of the measuring devices, or nearby servers where information will be communicated via models (expected ranges at this stage of few kilometres).

These measurements will then be converted after spatio-temporal aggregations to useful and forecastable timeseries that **POISZON** will process and visualise in conjunction with a **GIS** system too. The series will be at lower frequencies (reported a few times per day) in nanosievert per hour (nSv/h) and alerts will be raised, given when annual limits are expected to be reached, and the area of interest will be characterised longitudinally by a five-colour code (no risk, normal, low risk, high risk, eminent risk), and informing respective the interested stakeholders.

2.2 Usage Scenario 2

In our second usage scenario of POIS2ON socioeconomic stakeholders (e.g. a **mayor** of a local municipality near the area of interest) depict an area of interest in the sea where **anthropogenic activity** takes place like an underwater **Drilling for Oil** and respective risks are realised like in the case of BP and the Mexican Gulf and the Deepwater Horizon Oil Spill¹, and thus need to be measured. The area is indicated in a map, by either indicating a polygon of (latitude, longitude) for each corner of the polygon, or at a future extension a polygon of (latitude, longitude, depth from surface from, depth from surface to) for each corner of the polygon essentially depicting a 3D polygonal object in the water, as well a starting time and ending time (date/time) of observation. Then the RAMONES deployment team will break the 3D polygonal object into thousands of datapoints of (latitude, longitude, depth from surface) on which measurement will be made for the element of interest (e.g. Cs-137)

¹ <https://www.britannica.com/event/Deepwater-Horizon-oil-spill>

2.3 POIS2ON: High-level functional Requirements

The in-the-surface information system architecture for POIS2ON is depicted in **figure 1**:

Figure 1. RAMONES – Prototype F2SS with decentralized Repository

Where initially a decentralized repository is promoted. This is a necessity arising from the uncertainty around the development of our technologies in RAMONES and the fact that many of the devices used for the measurements will use local hard disks, local independent software and respective independent and initially isolated repositories and will communicate asynchronously via standard modems, thus no infrastructure for a fully centralized repository will be available. At a later stage as in **figure 2** a centralized version will be proposed, but not necessarily implemented within this project up to 2025.

Figure 2. RAMONES – Future implementation of Prototype F2SS with centralized Repository

In **figure 3** the connection with a GIS is proposed that will fully visualize the evolution of the low-frequency time series forecasted by POIS2ON and respective risks mapped in the respective color code.

Figure 3. RAMONES – Future implementation of Prototype F2SS with decentralized Repository and GIS

Figure 4. RAMONES – Functional sub-systems of Prototype F2SS

In **figure 4**, an initial suggested breakdown of POIS2ON in subsystems is proposed, a DSS, and FSS, a GIS, and RMIS to be finalized and discussed in detail in the next deliverable D5.2 : Repository, Information System and Risk no2 [due in month 24] - Repository, Information System and Risk, report (first - intermediate) on the design of the Information System

Figure 5. POIS2ON Prototype RAMONES Information System

In **figure 5** we see the final system, POIS2ON, that we will develop within this RAMONES project, while as future research specs for bigger and more scalable systems based on this prototype will be prescribed in with D5.4. once we know exactly the capabilities of the system been delivered.

3. Detailed Functional Requirements²

Project Description

Deliverable 5.1. of Work Package 5 provides the functional requirements for a prototype information system, hereafter referred to as **POIS2ON** (Prototype RAMONES Information System for SocioecONomic stakeholders), providing statistical forecasts and respective judgmental adjustments primarily for cumulative radionuclide concentrations, as well as other time series monitoring hazardous activities and respective risks. The prototype system POIS2ON, a Forecasting Support System (FSS), also proposes at this stage two alternative architectures for a repository (and respective databases – DB) for all recorded time series, with different levels of information concentration depending on the final form and capabilities of the technologies that will be developed from RAMONES.

Background and Dependent Deliverables

The deliverable 5.1 is the first of a series of eight deliverables D5.1 to D5.8, following every 6 months respectively, main outputs of T5.1 and T5.2 as stated in the GA. The functional requirements document (FRD) that is the main core of D5.1 is a formal statement of an application's functional requirements. It serves the same purpose as a foundation.

D5.1 is following and abiding to:

D6.6: Data Management Plan WP6 1 6

and is linked and creates a predicament for:

D5.2: Repository, Information System and Risk no2 [month 24], Repository, Information System and Risk, report (first - intermediate) on the design of the Information System

² Following the recommendations of all the necessary sections in a FRD (Functional Requirements Documents) as stated publicly available by Maryland.gov (has been awarded a 2018 Gold Award in the Government Websites category) from the Maryland Department of Information Technology; <https://www.maryland.gov/Pages/default.aspx>

D5.5: Forecasting and Risk Assessment for awareness policy support no1 [month 27], Forecasting and Risk Assessment for awareness policy support, report on the functional requirements of the data driven risk monitor at medium frequency for the awareness of interested stakeholders and communities health safety

Assumptions and Constraints

D5.1 and POIS2ON is developed in the assumption that the necessary measurements of respective radioactivity levels in the sea will be achievable through the technology developed by RAMONES at the prescribed high frequencies.

Interfaces to External Systems

POIS2ON will interface via APIs with all the decentralized and distributed repositories of each of the devices (mobile and static) of the RAMONES system, as well as governmental information systems of respective interested socioeconomic stakeholders. Owner of POIS2ON will be the RAMONES consortium as prescribed in the Grant Agreement and the respective anticipated Intellectual Property.

Points of Contact

Developer of POIS2ON is the RAMONES team of UDUR, with close collaboration in the design by the teams from ENS and UCA, and the rest of the RAMONES team in the testing phase of the prototype information system.

Document References

A series of meetings and respective non-transcribed interviews with all RAMONES partners formed the functional requirements of the POIS2ON system

Data Requirements

Measurements from the RAMONES mobile and static devices via the APIs of respective decentralized repositories

Functional Process Requirements

POIS2ON will process the respective measurement in time series of lower frequency and provide forecasts of these and respective alerts of when annual acceptable limits will be achieved.

Security

Clearance: “No user may access any part of this application who does not have at least a (specified) clearance.” There is a need to grant one type of user access to certain system functions but not to others, for example, administrator access.

Audit Trail

All activities will be recorded in the application’s audit trail.

Data Currency

All data will be kept in the system for each deployment of the system and then data stored by the stakeholder that requested the deployment

Reliability

Reliability is essential given the sensitive nature of the information stored and projected. Backup live systems will be enabled to secure this.

Recoverability

Full recoverability of data and forecasts is required.

System Availability

POIS2ON will be fully and constantly available through the time of the deployment of the RAMONES team *in situ*.

Fault Tolerance

The system should be able to collect data and forecast them intermittently so allowing for the possibility of some fault sin telecommunications – but normal frequencies of reporting should be restored the soonest possible.

Performance

Real time response and provision of forecasts within less than an hour with a combination of statistical, ML and DL methods.

Capacity

System should run in an off-the-shelf laptop of no more than (current cost) of 2000 Euros.

Data Retention

Data retained for each deployment of RAMONES and then passed and stored by the respective socioeconomic stakeholders that required, authorized and reimbursed the deployment. All processes abide to the already submitted and approved by the consortium Data Management Plan (DMP) as in D6.6: Data Management Plan WP6 1 6

4. Conclusion and the Future

RAMONES aspires to introduce novel monitoring and response channels to inform key socio-political and socio-economics stakeholders at regular intervals at medium (daily, weekly) to low (monthly to inter-annually) frequencies. To that end, the deliverable 5.1. of Work Package 5 provides the functional requirements for a prototype information system, hereafter referred to as **POIS2ON** (Prototype RAMONES Information System for SocioecONomic stakeholders), an amalgamation of the French words 'fish' and 'poison' to indicate the risk of deep sea anthropogenic and natural emitted radioactivity to our ecosystem and respective food chain. POIS2ON will provide statistical forecasts and respective judgmental adjustments primarily for cumulative radionuclide concentrations as well as other time series monitoring hazardous activities and respective risks.

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